

Prosthodontic Practice in Covid-19 : A Review

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Abstract

Prosthodontists along with other dental professionals may encounter patients that could be COVID positive and will have to provide care to the patient but at the same time they also have prevent the spread of infection. Prosthodontists are at a high risk of exposure to patient's infected saliva and blood so it is of utmost importance to treat the patient in such a way that further transmission of the disease can be prevented. The aim of this article is to provide a brief overview of general and self-protective measures and the treatment that can be performed during this pandemic.

Keyword: COVID-19, Emergency Treatment Need, Pandemic, Prosthodontic Consideration

Introduction

Coronavirus disease is caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus which is a single-stranded enveloped RNA virus of the Beta coronavirus family and enters the human cells through Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2 (ACE-2) receptors with the help of its S (spike) protein^[1]. The SARS-CoV-2 virus has a diameter in the range of 60-140 nm and the main route of spread is through person to person contact or by direct exposure to infected respiratory droplets^[2]. It can also spread through asymptomatic carriers which is the reason why there is concern among dental practitioners.

Dentists are at very high risk of acquiring the infection because of the involvement of oral fluids, aerosol generation, and exposure to the blood. Hence Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and other disinfection protocols need to be followed.

Prosthodontic procedures require some modifications during this Covid-era. Prosthodontists have to deal with saliva and blood-contaminated instruments and articles which can serve as a source of the disease transmission. Aerosol-generating instruments are also one of the main concerns as they amplify the spread of the virus particles many folds^[3]. Prosthodontists require constant lab support so extra precaution needs to be taken to prevent the transmission of the virus because apart from the dentist there are multiple lab technicians involved performing various tasks. Prosthodontics provides treatment to patients of all age groups consisting of geriatric patients, patients requiring Maxillofacial prosthesis (MFP) following cancer or trauma or mucormycosis infection so involvement of

such a variety of patients makes it crucial to form proper treatment protocol and guidelines. Geriatric patients are more Prone to acquire infection because of lower immunity and the presence of comorbidities like diabetes, various cardiovascular and respiratory illnesses, so it's of utmost importance to prevent the transmission of the infection^[4].

India has the 2nd highest number of confirmed covid cases in the world and the 3rd highest number of covid deaths. As of now the new omicron variant of the virus has shown a rise in the spread and is expected to achieve the peak in February 2022. So an effort has been made to review old literature and protocols to suggest some modifications in the procedures performed and to ensure the safety of all the patients and the dentist.

Implications of Covid-19 in Prosthodontics

Prosthodontists are at high risk of exposure to the infection because of either direct or indirect contact with a possible covid infected individual in the following ways-

- Exposure to saliva during various procedures like impression making.
- Aerosols are produced due to the use of high-speed rotary instruments which facilitate the spread of infection.
- Contaminated acrylic debris from the patient's prosthesis can be source of infection.
- Involvement of dental lab and technicians always runs a risk in the transmission of the virus as there is involvement of multiple people for a case.^{[5][6]}

Saliva & SARS-CoV-2

The main targets of the SARS-CoV-2 are

those cells that express angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE 2)^[7]. ACE 2 acts as a receptor for the virus entry into the cell. Salivary gland epithelial cells express ACE 2 which is why the salivary gland gets infected with the virus and hence the saliva produced by it is a potential source of infection either directly or indirectly.^[8]

Teledentistry

The first mode of interaction between the dentist and the patient should be over a video call. In this way, the dentist can evaluate the severity of the patient's illness and can categorize the procedure into an emergency or urgent one^[9]. Questions should be asked to the patient whether he/she have had a fever, cough, sore throat, shortness of breath, close contact with people suspected to have a covid-19 infection In the last 14 days^[10]. The dentist has the autonomy to reschedule the appointment when the patient gives a positive answer to any of the above questions. The patient is asked to come at least 14 days after the onset of the symptoms.

Prosthodontic Treatments to be Performed

All the elective treatment can be postponed only emergency and urgent procedures are performed, in situations like the following –^[11]

- Need for surgical and interim obturators
- Caries or pain in abutment of fixed prosthesis
- Peri-implantitis
- Infection around the prosthesis
- Mobile/fixed faulty prosthesis
- Dislodged prosthesis
- Broken prosthesis
- Need for temporary or immediate dentures
- Ulceration due to prosthesis or sharp tooth.

Preventive Measures During Dental Care

Use of slow speed hand piece producing less aerosol, hand piece with anti-retraction valves, high volume saliva ejectors, high vacuum extra oral suctions, rubber dams where more amount of aerosols are generated, digital impression making, four-handed dentistry, Personal Protective Equipment are suggested^[12]. Imaging procedures should use extraoral techniques including OPG and CBCT to avoid contact with saliva and to prevent gag reflex^[10]. If intra oral imaging has to be done then double barrier should be used over the sensor to prevent cross-infection.

Patients should be asked to rinse the oral cavity with 1.5 % hydrogen peroxide or 0.2% povidone-iodine^[7]. When rubber dam isolation is not possible then this measure is highly recommended. In the case of paediatric patients where rinsing cannot be done, cotton soaked with these solutions should be used^[7]. Studies have shown that hydrogen peroxide (0.5%) and povidone-iodine (0.2%) inactivates the virus after one minute of use^[8].

Role of Personal Protective Equipment

Dentists who are exposed to aerosol must use N95-type

mask, face shield, waterproof disposable gowns along with head cap and gloves^[13]. N95 mask filters aerosol in a very effective way and is way better than the normal surgical mask. Viral particles from respiratory secretion can travel via aerosol (<5 microns in diameter) or droplets (>5 microns in diameter)^[14]. The N95 mask is capable of filtering 0.3 microns particles by 95% on the other hand surgical masks can filter particles of 5 microns or more^[10]. N95 mask provides 2-way protection, Masks with valves protect only the wearer while on the other hand triple-layered mask only protect people of surrounding not the wearer. Reuse of these N95 masks and respirators with valves should not be reused as it has no evidence-based recommendation^[15].

Inactivation & Prevention of Contamination From Coronavirus

Aerosols are produced in large quantities while doing professional prophylaxis, using rotary instruments for tooth preparations or during trimming, finishing and polishing of prosthesis contaminated with saliva. Aerosol may contain both large and small particles (> 5 microns and <5 microns respectively). Large particles may settle down due to gravity but the smaller ones can travel in air up to 1.5 to 2 meters and it can remain viable for up to 3 hours suspended in air^[7]. Viral load in aerosol is variable. During normal breathing, it is 0.34 copies /cm³ but it can reach up to 11.5 copies /cm³. While coughing it can go up to 366,000 copies /cm³^[15]. Only the essential items should be kept in the open while all the other materials and instruments should be kept in closed cabinets.

In clinics where proper ventilation cannot be maintained use of air filters is recommended using high-efficiency particulate arrestor (HEPA) filters. HEPA filter can remove up to 99.97% of particles measuring 0.3 microns from the air^[10]. HEPA 13 or 14 are generally recommended according to their filtration efficiency. Another way of purifying the air of coronavirus is by using negative ion generators, it fills the air with millions of negative ions which helps in breaking the lipid layer of the virus and reduces the viral load^[6].

Fumigation and fogging are the other two methods for disinfecting clinics only where the circulation of clean air is possible post procedure^[8]. For fumigation, formaldehyde solution is mixed with fixed proportion of potassium permanganate, this combination gives rise to fumes, which can kill bacteria, fungus along with their spores but it is not done commonly today because formaldehyde is a known carcinogen. On the other hand fogging can be done with mixture of hydrogen peroxide and silver ion solution or third-generation quaternary ammonium compounds. Fogging is comparatively rapid, effective and does not leave residue which makes it a preferred technique for the clinics and the labs. This method usually takes up to 45 min followed by a dwell time of an hour^[8].

UV-C rays (wavelength 200-280nm) can also be used to disinfect clinics and labs^[10]. It is safe, doesn't leave any residue, has a wide spectrum of germicidal activity and can be used in the presence of human beings.

Aerosol can deposit on inanimate surfaces in the office, so the

use of biocidal agents over these surfaces is necessary, there should be an adequate interval between two patients so that the clinical setup can be properly cleaned and disinfected. Among different biocidal agents, ethanol (78–95%), propan-2-ol (70–100%), 45% propan-2-ol associated with 30% propan-1-ol, glutaraldehyde (0.5–2.5%), formaldehyde (0.7–1%), and povidone-iodine (0.23–7.5%) are shown to reduce infectivity of the coronavirus by about 10,000 times or more^[13]. The minimum effective concentration of sodium hypochlorite is 0.21% and hydrogen peroxide is 0.5%^[7].

Recommendations For Clinic Setup

The clinic should have dedicated areas for particular procedures including a separate sterilization room

- **Waiting Area-**

Basic information of the patient is taken, sanitization through contactless dispensers, noncontact temperature recording, patient is given face mask, shoe covers, head cap, gloves, glass barrier can be installed at the reception counter to prevent transmission of droplets. The patient is asked to fill the screening form and an informed consent in his/her preferred language. It is recommended to have a pulse oximeter, it measures arterial oxygen saturation very quickly^[16]. If the oxygen saturation is below 93% then the patient should be referred to the physician for detailed screening^[12].

- **Screening Area-**

Initial screening and diagnosis are done here. Pre-procedural mouth rinse is advised using povidone-iodine 0.5% for at least 15s can deactivate the virus completely. Other chemical based mouth rinses which can disrupt the viral lipid membrane include ethanol, chlorhexidine, cetylpyridinium chloride and hydrogen peroxide.

Orthopantomogram (OPG) and cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) are recommended instead of intraoral radiographs to prevent contamination from saliva. But, OPG doesn't give good resolution and CBCT exposes the patient to higher radiation dose as compared to intraoral radiographs^[16].

- **Non-Aerosol Generating Area-**

Here the procedures are performed with the use of hand instruments such as spoon excavator and chemical-based agents to remove caries, hand scaling etc. Donning and Doffing of PPE is done in specific area followed by sequential steps. Use of four-handed dentistry and digital workflow is suggested^[16].

- **Aerosol Generating Area-**

This area involves the use of high-speed hand piece leading to production of aerosols in large quantities. This area involves a high risk of transmission therefore it's mandatory to follow universal precautions /OSHO guidelines^[10]. Only the essential articles should be kept open while others should be kept in closed cabinets. Clinician should avoid the 8 o'clock chair position to avoid direct contact with the splatter^[16].

Conclusion

The intent of this review was to discuss the effect of covid-19 on dental practice as prosthodontists are at high risk of acquiring covid infection due to production and exposure to a lot of aerosol and possibly contaminated surfaces and indirect contact with dental laboratories and dental technicians. Therefore it has become very important for dental practitioners to incorporate all precautionary measures in their routine practice and additional safety measures if treatment of patients with COVID-19 becomes necessary as the omicron cases are rising rapidly.

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